

Farm Pond Designs for Moderate to High Rainfall Zone of Marathwada Region based on Rainfall-Runoff Relationship

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Abstract:

Accurately designed farm ponds enhance water storage and agricultural resilience during Marathwada's dry spells and variable monsoon patterns. In this study, runoff was estimated using the SCS Curve Number method, which considered various parameters such as soil type and vegetation. The rainfall-runoff relationship was analysed to facilitate the planning of small water harvesting structures, like farm ponds. The runoff potential was found to be 31.69% of the rainfall, indicating significant opportunities for rainwater harvesting and the construction of additional site-specific structures. The established rainfall-runoff relationship is represented by the equation $Y = 0.608X - 209.2$, with an R^2 value of 0.9575. This linear relationship will aid in predicting runoff for any rainfall event in the area, allowing for a more accurate determination of rainwater harvesting potential and its reuse for enhancing the productivity of various rainfed crops. Given the climatic variations in the last decade—particularly concerning rainfall intensity, duration, and frequency—there is a need to redesign farm pond sizes in Marathwada's rain-scarce zones for effective implementation of the farm pond program. The recommended farm pond sizes include storage capacities of 939 cum, 1,677 cum, and 2,811 cum for catchment areas of 1 ha, 2 ha, and 3 ha, respectively. Based on these storage capacities, square-shaped farm ponds with top dimensions of 22 x 22 m, 28 x 28 m, and 35 x 35 m, a depth of 3 m, and a trapezoidal side slope of 1.5:1 are proposed for the State Department of Agriculture's implementation.

Key words: Curve number, farm pond, micro- catchment, rainfall, runoff

Introduction

Rainfed agriculture supports 40 percent of the global population and contributes 44 percent to India's total food production (Singh and Singh, 2017). The fate of rainfed agriculture depends on the quantity and distribution of monsoon rains, making rainwater conservation crucial for stabilizing and enhancing productivity. Droughts, occurring frequently across

different parts of the country, further reduce total agricultural output. Farmers in dry regions will be the most affected by climate change in the future, necessitating diverse coping strategies for adaptation.

Runoff estimation is vital for designing water harvesting structures, as these play an important role in managing water resources efficiently. Runoff, a key hydrologic variable, is influenced largely by rainfall intensity (Kundzewicz and Arnell, 2008). Other factors, such as rainfall duration, intensity, and aerial distribution, also affect the rate and volume of runoff. Catchment characteristics like slope, shape, size, soil cover, and rainfall duration directly influence peak flow and runoff volume (Chandler and Walker, 1998). Over the past decade, climatic variations have led to uneven rainfall and runoff distribution, affecting agricultural productivity.

The Marathwada region of Maharashtra is traditionally drought-prone, with annual rainfall ranging from 500 to 1100 mm, and around 20 per cent of the area is classified as moderate to high rainfall (900 to 1100 mm/year) zones. Rainfall in this region is often erratic, and severe droughts frequently occur. Crop productivity declines due to both insufficient rainfall and uneven distribution, which can cause moisture stress at critical growth stages during dry spells, particularly in July and August. These conditions underscore the importance of rainwater harvesting for ensuring sustainable crop production.

Rainwater harvesting structures can help store water for agricultural use during dry periods, contributing to increased resilience in crop production. Around 20 per cent of Marathwada falls within the moderate to high rainfall zone (Bawankar et al., 2012). However, the region still experiences two to three prolonged dry spells during the crop growth period. These dry spells significantly reduce crop productivity and adversely affect farmers' socio-economic conditions. The average productivity of kharif crops fluctuates based on monsoon behaviour.

To address this challenge, properly designed farm ponds based on runoff potential are essential for efficient water storage and sustainable crop production. By capturing and storing rainwater, farmers can better manage water resources and reduce their vulnerability to climate-related risks.

Material and methods

For estimating the runoff potential, daily rainfall data for the moderate to high rainfall zone (Nanded station) from 2011 to 2021 was collected from the Meteorological Observatory at the All India Coordinated Research Project on Agro-Meteorology (AICRPAM), VNMKV, Parbhani (Latitude: 19.1383° N, Longitude: 77.3209° E). The daily runoff for each runoff-producing rainfall event was estimated using the Soil Conservation Service (SCS) Curve Number (CN) method. The rainfall and runoff data were analysed and grouped fortnightly to understand runoff potential over time.

The SCS Curve Number technique is based on the recharge capacity of the watershed, which depends on antecedent moisture conditions and the physical characteristics of the watershed.

Antecedent Moisture Condition (AMC) serves as an index of watershed wetness (Ponce and Hawkins, 1996). In this study, the Hydrological Soil Group (HSG, which plays a critical role in runoff production) of the area was considered as Group "D", representing soils with low infiltration rates. The selection of curve numbers was based on various factors such as hydrologic soil cover, land use, treatment or cultivation practices, hydrological conditions, and the HSG of the area.

Using the standard equations for runoff estimation in black soil regions, the SCS Curve Number technique was applied to determine runoff potential. Available maps of land use/land cover and HSG were used to estimate the area of each land class. Curve numbers suitable for each land use and HSG were assigned, and the weighted curve number for the watershed was calculated. This weighted curve number was then used to estimate the runoff potential of the study area. Studies by Amutha and Porchelvan (2009), Bansode and Patil (2014), Bhura et al. (2015), and Mishra et al. (2005) have successfully utilised the SCS Curve Number method for similar runoff estimations, and the same methodology was applied here.

The fortnightly runoff volume was calculated based on the runoff potential of the standard catchment area. Factors like pan evaporation and seepage rates through the soil strata were also considered to determine the cumulative runoff potential for farm ponds. With these factors in mind, the runoff volume that could be harvested was estimated, and the sizes of farm ponds suitable for various catchment areas were calculated accordingly.

This approach provides an effective framework for estimating runoff potential and designing water harvesting structures in regions like Nanded, where rainfall is often moderate to high. This method can help farmers manage water resources efficiently by proper designing of farm ponds, ensuring better water availability for agricultural purposes during dry spells.

Results and Discussion

Estimation of Curve Numbers

CN values were estimated based on the hydrologic soil group, the average slope of the land and the land use pattern of the area for the moderate to high rainfall zone of the Marathwada region. The weighted values of curve numbers for three AMC conditions were calculated using the USDA SCS-CN method. The hydrologic soil group for the region was observed as 'D' with a slope range of 0.5 to 3.0 %. The weighted curve numbers were calculated as 79, 91 and 97 for AMC-I, AMC-II and AMC-III, respectively.

Estimation of runoff volume

The daily surface runoff was estimated, thereby establishing the yearly runoff data for the moderate to high rainfall zone of the Marathwada region (Table 1). The average runoff was calculated, and the maximum runoff year was also noted.

Table 1: Yearly rainfall, runoff, % runoff and runoff coefficient for moderate to high rainfall zone

Year	Annual Rainfall (mm)	Rainfall (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Runoff (%)	Runoff coefficient
2011	708.1	697.1	205.3	29.45	0.294
2012	662.7	662.7	122.2	18.43	0.184
2013	1111.9	1091.6	414.2	37.94	0.379
2014	436.5	434	99	22.81	0.228
2015	599	465.2	71	15.26	0.152
2016	1124.8	1094	479.7	43.84	0.438
2017	641.8	633.6	161.5	25.48	0.254
2018	799.5	749.8	272.8	36.38	0.363
2019	1027.1	1007.7	344	34.13	0.341
2020	924.7	918.9	368.9	40.14	0.401
2021	1293.4	1230.3	550	44.70	0.447
Average	848.13	816.81	280.78	31.69	0.316
Maximum	1293.4	1230.3	550	44.70	0.44

The average rainfall causing runoff was found to be 816.81 mm, which generated a mean runoff of 280.78 mm, i.e. 31.69 per cent. The maximum rainfall causing runoff was recorded as 1293.4 mm in the year 2021 and had a runoff potential of 550 mm (44.70 per cent). The data related to extreme/ heavy rainfall events for the moderate to heavy rainfall zone during the years 2011 to 2021 (Table 2).

Table 2: Extreme/heavy rainfall events in the moderate to heavy rainfall zone of Marathwada Region

Years	July		August		September	
	Date	Rainfall, mm	Date	Rainfall, mm	Date	Rainfall, mm
2013	17.7.13	54.1	1.8.13	56.2	-	-
2016	12.7.16	77.2	24.8.16	50.8	-	-
2017	-	-	20.8.17	97.4	-	-
2018	-	-	21.8.18	78.1	-	-
2019	-	-	3.8.19	56.9	1.9.19	50.7
2021	12.7.21	57.1	-	-	8.9.21	62.2
	22.7.21	62.8	-	-	9.9.21	54.3
	-	-	-	-	28.9.21	90.4

Out of the 11-year period, heavy rainfall events were observed in 6 years, which generated maximum runoff.

Rainfall-runoff relationship for moderate to high rainfall zone of Marathwada region

Vinithra and Yeshodha (2013) developed a rainfall-runoff model using SCS-CN method as a case study of Krishnagiri district, Tamil Nadu state. Similarly, Satheesh Kumar et al. (2017) conducted a study on a rainfall-runoff relationship using SCS-CN and GIS approach for the Pappiredipatti watershed of the Vaniyar sub-basin, South India.

In the present study, a rainfall-runoff relationship was obtained to determine the runoff corresponding to any rainfall occurring in the study area. The relationship was found to be linear and is expressed as $Y = 0.608X - 209.2$ with the R^2 value of 0.96.

Design of Farm ponds for moderate to high rainfall zone of Marathwada region

Farm ponds were designed based on the rainfall-runoff relationship expected evaporation and seepage losses during the monsoon season and also according to the catchment areas of 1 ha, 2 ha and 3 ha, and the average size of land holding of the farmers of the region. The size and storage capacity of farm ponds depend on runoff potential from the catchment area, and accordingly, the farm ponds were designed for all three stations, viz. Aurangabad, Parbhani and Nanded stations, respectively (Table 3).

The runoff volume was estimated by the end of each fortnight for 1ha, 2 ha and 3 ha catchment areas, respectively. Dependable runoff from the catchment areas was considered as 80%, and adding current rainfall in the pond and then subtracting the expected storage losses (Seepage and evaporation), fortnightly runoff and cumulative runoff volumes, expected to be harvested, were estimated. Based on the expected runoff volume, the tentative size of the farm pond was worked out. According to the top surface area of the farm pond and average evaporation rate, the water loss during the fortnight was worked out. Similarly, seepage losses were estimated based on the size of the pond. Pond evaporation losses are calculated by multiplying the surface area of ponded water with open pan evaporation of that fortnight with a pan coefficient of 0.70. The seepage rate is taken as constant as 20 mm/day, and seepage losses are calculated by multiplying the seepage rate by the surface area of ponded water (Tables 4,5, and 6).

Table 3: Year-wise Fortnightly rainfall-runoff for moderate to high rainfall zone of Marathwada region

Year	June		July				August				September				October					
	1-15		16-30		1-15		16-31		1-15		16-31		1-15		16-31		1-15		16-31	
	Rainfall	Runoff	Rainfall	Runoff	Rainfall	Runoff	Rainfall	Runoff	Rainfall	Runoff	Rainfall	Runoff								
2011	46.4	0	46.7	5	140.	53	70.1	9	104	49	189	82	54.9	4	35.4	2.5	9.3	0	0	0
2012	7.6	0	101	31	78.7	8	140.	39.1	48.6	0	107	18.	86.6	18.5	39.1	3.5	52.8	3	0	0
2013	120.8	27	82.9	19.5	148	47	279	173	161	91	57.7	19	45.7	4	82.8	15	93	16	19.7	2
2014	11.7	0	17.6	0	44.9	0	45.9	0	43.7	0	151	63	96.2	36	16.5	0	1.6	0	4.4	0
2015	66.2	9	90.3	34	8	0	43.7	0	85.1	3	44.4	0	69.9	0	48	25	9.5	0	0	0
2016	49.9	3	164.6	68.5	178.	85	173.	70	52.6	23	49.8	17	91.9	40	209	108	123.9	65	0	0
2017	77.6	7	90.1	22	30.1	0	78.3	30	44.7	2.5	188.	93	33.5	0	31.8	2	47.2	5	11.8	0
2018	162.5	76	79.9	6	116	30	46.5	5	50.7	6	250	149	18.4	0	24.2	0	0.1	0	0.3	0
2019	14.3	0	77.5	6.2	65.6	7.8	159	54	168	89	57.2	12	144	60	135	47	39.6	2	146.2	61.5
2020	81.2	3	64.8	4	131.	51	98.6	5	103	5	100	34	98.6	23	166	77	62.9	2	10.7	0
2021	142.8	50	82.3	18	205	121	182	107	13	0	168.	60	197.	109	177	84	26.2	1	35.3	0

Table 4: Design of Farm pond for 1 ha catchment area for moderate to high rainfall Zone of Marathwada region

Month	Duration	Rainfall (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Runoff volume (m ³)for 1 ha area)	Dependable runoff volume (80%) (m ³)	Rainfall In pond (m ³)	Total (m ³)	Expected Evaporation from Pond (m ³)	Expected Seepage Losses from pond (m ³)	Expected Run. Volume (m ³)	Expected Cumulative Runoff volume (m ³)	Remark
June	7-15	71	15.90	159	127	34.36	161.36	28.11	23.78	109.47	109.47	
	16-30	81.60	19.47	194	155	39.49	194.49	48.12	34.70	111.67	221.14	1 st
July	1-15	104.35	36.61	366	292	50.50	342.5	39.71	30.20	272.59	493.73	filling
	16-31	119.79	44.78	447	357	57.97	414.97	38.12	33.00	343.85	837.58	of farm
Aug	1-15	79.70	24.40	244	195	38.57	233.57	35.42	28.70	169.45	1007.03	pond
	16-31	124.16	49.88	498	398	60.09	458.09	39.01	34.40	384.68	1391.71	2 nd
Sept.	1-15	85.2	26.77	267	213	41.23	254.23	36.10	31.60	186.53	1578.24	filling
	16-31	87.86	33.15	331	264	42.52	306.52	35.23	39.50	231.79	1810.03	of farm
Oct.	1-15	42.37	8.54	854	683	20.50	703.5	38.72	49.70	615.08	2425.11	pond
	16-31	20.76	5.77	577	461	10.04	471.04	44.67	54.0	372.37	2797.48	3 rd

Size of farm pond
 Top – 22m x 22m
 Bottom – 13mx13m
 Depth – 3 m
 Side slope – 1.5:1
 Volume of storage: 939 Cum

Area irrigated = 1.6 ha
 No. of irrigation = 2
 Depth of irrigation = 5 cm

Table 5: Design of Farm pond for 2 ha catchment area for moderate to high rainfall Zone of Marathwada region

Month	Duration	Rainfall (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Runoff volume (m ³)for 2ha area)	Dependable runoff volume (80%) (m ³)	Rainfall In pond (m ³)	Total (m ³)	Expected Evaporation from Pond (m ³)	Expected Seepage Losses from pond (m ³)	Run. Volume At the end of runoff (m ³)	Cumulative Runoff volume (m ³)	Remark
June	7-15	71	15.90	318	254.4	55.66	310.06	45.54	32.70	231.82	231.82	
	16-30	81.60	19.47	388	310.4	63.97	374.37	77.96	46.50	249.91	481.73	1 st filling of farm pond
July	1-15	104.35	36.61	732	585.6	82.81	668.41	64.33	44.10	559.98	1041.71	
	16-31	119.79	44.78	894	715.2	93.91	809.11	38.12	43.50	727.49	1769.2	
Aug.	1-15	79.70	24.40	488	390.4	62.48	452.88	57.38	42.60	352.9	2122.1	2 nd filling of farm pond
	16-31	124.16	49.88	996	796.8	97.34	894.14	63.19	46.50	784.45	2906.55	
Sept.	1-15	85.2	26.77	534	427.2	66.79	493.99	58.48	46.60	388.91	3295.46	
	16-31	87.86	33.15	662	529.6	68.88	598.48	58.69	52.50	487.29	3782.75	
Oct.	1-15	42.37	8.54	1708	1366.4	33.21	1399.61	62.72	60.40	1276.49	5059.24	3 rd filling of farm pond
	16-31	20.76	5.77	1154	923.2	16.27	939.47	72.36	64.20	802.91	5862.15	

Size of farm pond

Top – 28 m x 28 m

Bottom – 19 mx19 m

Depth – 3 m

Side slope – 1.5:1

Volume of storage: 1677 Cum

Area irrigated = 2.8 ha

No. of irrigation = 2

Depth of irrigation = 5 cm

Table 6: Farm pond design for 3 ha catchment area for moderate to high rainfall Zone of Marathwada region

Month	Duration	Rainfall (mm)	Runoff (mm)	Runoff volume (m ³)for 3ha area)	Dependable runoff volume (80%) (m ³)	Rainfall In pond (m ³)	Total (m ³)	Expected Evaporation from Pond (m ³)	Expected Seepage Losses from pond (m ³)	Run. Volume At the end of runoff (m ³)	Cumulative Runoff volume (m ³)	Remark
June	7-15	71	15.90	477	381.6	86.97	468.57	71.16	46.20	351.21	351.21	
	16-30	81.60	19.47	582	465.6	99.96	565.56	115.68	66.70	383.18	734.39	1 st filling of farm pond
July	1-15	104.35	36.61	1098	878.4	127.82	1006.22	100.52	59.20	846.5	1580.89	
	16-31	119.79	44.78	1341	1072.8	146.74	1219.54	96.49	63.00	1060.05	2640.94	
Aug.	1-15	79.70	24.40	732	585.6	97.63	683.23	89.67	55.50	538.06	3179.00	2 nd filling of farm pond
	16-31	124.16	49.88	1494	1195.2	152.09	1347.29	98.73	64.50	1184.06	4363.06	
Sept.	1-15	85.2	26.77	801	640.8	104.37	745.17	91.38	59.60	594.19	4957.25	
	16-31	87.86	33.15	993	794.4	107.62	902.02	91.71	72.50	737.81	5695.06	
Oct.	1-15	42.37	8.54	2562	2049.6	51.90	2101.5	98	89.70	1913.8	7608.86	3 rd filling of farm pond
	16-31	20.76	5.77	1731	1384.8	25.43	1410.23	113.06	95.00	1202.17	8811.03	

Size of farm pond
 Top – 35m x 35m
 Bottom – 26mx26m
 Depth – 3 m
 Side slope – 1.5:1
 Volume of storage: 2811 Cum.

Area irrigated = 2.25 ha
 No. of irrigation = 2
 Depth of irrigation = 5 cm

Based on design parameters, 1007.03 cum, 1769.2 cum and 2640.39 cum of runoff volume will be expected to be harvested for 1 ha, 2 ha and 3 ha catchment areas, respectively. Accordingly, the farm ponds of capacity 939 cum, 1677 cum and 2811 cum were designed for 1 ha, 2 ha and 3 ha catchment areas, respectively (Table 7).

Table 7: Farm Pond sizes for moderate to high rainfall zone of Marathwada region

Catchment Area, ha	Top Size of pond (m x m)	Bottom Size of pond (m x m)	Side slope	Depth of farm pond (m)	Capacity of farm pond (Cum)	Area under 2 irrigation of 5 cm depth (ha)	Area irrigated of catchment area (%)	Catchment Area under pond construction (%)
1	22 x 22	13 x 13	1.5: 1	3	939	1.60	75	4.84
2	28 x 28	19 x 19	1.5: 1	3	1677	2.14	75	3.92
3	35 x 35	26 x 26	1.5: 1	3	2811	4.22	75	4.08

If runoff is harvested, the stored water can be used for protective irrigation during dry spells during the *khari* season. For normal monsoon season, the farm ponds would get refilled three times before the withdrawal of monsoon and this stored water can be used to provide supplemental irrigation to *rabi* crops for production enhancement.

Conclusion

The relationship between rainfall and runoff proved to be the most valuable information for designing farm ponds as rainwater harvesting structures. The runoff potential for the moderate to high rainfall zone of the Marathwada region was found to be 31.7 %. A linear relationship between rainfall and runoff was developed to estimate the runoff potential for the study area. For moderate to high rainfall zones of the Marathwada region, farm ponds of 939 cum, 1677 cum and 2811 cum storage capacities were designed for 1 ha, 2 ha and 3 ha catchment areas, respectively.

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